

DYSARTHRIA: MODERN CLASSIFICATION, CLINICAL FEATURES AND CORRECTION APPROACHES

V.T.Axmedova

Andijan State

Pedagogical Institute Department of Special

Pedagogy ORCID ID 009-003-6218-0270

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Scientific literature, journal articles, and clinical guidelines were analyzed.

Special attention was given to neurological foundations, clinical symptoms, modern diagnostic procedures, and correction approaches

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problem of dysarthria and highlights its modern classification, main clinical manifestations, and correction methods.

Dysarthria is a complex pathology caused by organic damage to the central or peripheral nervous system, characterized by impairment of the articulatory (sound-producing) aspect of speech.

The paper examines neurological classifications of dysarthria (bulbar, pseudobulbar, subcortical, cerebellar, and cortical) as well as severity-based classifications (erased, mild, moderate, and severe).

Special attention is given to the etiology, symptomatology, diagnosis, and modern treatment approaches of subcortical and cerebellar dysarthria. Diagnostic criteria and comprehensive rehabilitation approaches are also analyzed.

Introduction

Dysarthria is a disorder of the articulatory aspect of speech resulting from impaired innervation of the speech apparatus.

Disturbance in neural transmission to articulatory muscles leads to speech motor dysfunction. The causes include vascular diseases, traumatic brain injuries, infections, tumors, and degenerative processes.

Clinically, dysarthria manifests in articulation defects, voice changes, impaired stress placement, and speech motor pathology.

In severe cases, complete loss of speech production (anarthria) may occur.

Methods

Scientific literature, journal articles, and clinical guidelines were analyzed.

Special attention was given to neurological foundations, clinical symptoms, modern diagnostic procedures, and correction approaches.

Results and Discussion Modern Classification of Dysarthria According to ICD-10, dysarthria is coded as R47.1.

Neurological classification (based on lesion localization):

- Bulbar dysarthria – lesion of cranial nerve nuclei in the medulla oblongata.

- Pseudobulbar dysarthria – damage to corticobulbar pathways.
- Subcortical (extrapyramidal) dysarthria – lesion of subcortical nuclei.
- Cerebellar dysarthria – pathology of the cerebellum and its pathways.
- Cortical dysarthria – focal cortical lesions.

Severity classification:

- Erased (minimal) dysarthria
- Mild dysarthria
- Moderate dysarthria
- Severe dysarthria (anarthria) Subcortical Dysarthria

Etiology includes traumatic brain injury, vascular pathology, inflammation, toxic damage, and stress; congenital cases are also possible.

Symptoms include impaired muscle tone, disrupted coordination, speech tempo disturbances, repetition of syllables, changes in voice timbre, and unclear articulation.

Treatment includes management of the underlying disease, neuroimaging (CT, MRI, EEG), medication therapy, and speech therapy.

Cerebellar Dysarthria

Etiology includes hemorrhagic stroke, trauma, neurosurgery, encephalitis, tumors, multiple sclerosis, and ataxia.

Speech is scanning, explosive, slow, unclear, with altered phonation and nasalization. Coordination disturbances and gait instability are common.

Treatment includes pathogenetic therapy, speech therapy exercises, rehabilitation, and physiotherapy.

Erased and Mild Dysarthria

Characterized by minor articulation defects and slight prosodic disturbances. Speech is understandable but unclear.

Severe swallowing disorders are usually absent.

Diagnosis and Treatment

Diagnosis includes neurological and speech therapy assessment, EEG, electromyography, MRI, CT, and Doppler studies.

Comprehensive treatment includes:

- Medication therapy (vitamins, nootropics)
- Physiotherapy and rehabilitation (exercise therapy, massage, swimming, acupuncture)
- Speech therapy correction (articulation exercises, breathing training, sound automation)
- Speech therapy massage (including probe massage)
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Conclusion

Dysarthria is a complex speech disorder requiring interdisciplinary cooperation between neurologists, speech therapists, and rehabilitation specialists.

Neurological classification assists in selecting pathogenetic therapy, while severity classification guides correction planning.

Modern diagnostic technologies (MRI, CT, EEG) enable accurate lesion localization. Comprehensive rehabilitation significantly improves speech function and quality of life.

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